

ISic1307

I.Sicily inscription 1307

Language

Latin and Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

6 miles out

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140799

1. D (is) □ M (anibus) □ s (acrum) □
2. Κλωδία Βαλεντεΐνα
3. χαΐρε· ἔζη ²⁷ἔζη(σεν)²⁷ ἔ (τη) XXXX
4. ἐποίησε ἰδίᾳ γυναι-
5. κὶ Ἰγναΐτις Κάρικος
6. μνή (μης) χάριν.
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492912

EDCS 39101677

PHI 140799

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0484 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. *Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum*. Berlin. At 3.5396

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